

Resisting a narrow vision of public interest

Insights and policy recommendations from the ACCTING project

February 2025

The aim of this document is to provide policy recommendations to reframe and democratise the concept of "public interest". While often invoked in policy and decision-making, the term is politically charged and remains vague. This ambiguity can prevent communities from engaging in meaningful discussions about their collective priorities and rights. Policymakers, institutions and communities must shift focus from imposing top-down definitions of public interest to foster inclusive, transparent processes that enable diverse voices to define and pursue shared goals. This document provides recommendations to help communities and policymakers foster a collective vision of public interest that is inclusive, dynamic, and responsive to societal needs. By empowering communities, activist groups, NGOs, media, and academia to reclaim and reshape public interest, this approach supports the European Green Deal's vision that "citizens are, and should remain, a driving force of the transition" towards sustainability (EC, 2019, p. 22).

Recommendations

The recommendations below are primarily directed towards i) civil society organisations, ii) policy makers and a set of recommendations here are directed towards iii) both actors.

I: Scrutinising top-down public interest

Authorities often weaponise the term “public interest” to shut down critiques of new or unpopular policies. Civil society actors need to:

1. **Highlight misuse:** Document and publicise cases where “public interest” is used to suppress critique, justify unpopular policies or bypass the process of public participation in decision making.
2. **Demand accountability:** Advocate for transparency and accountability in decision-making processes to expose how authorities invoke “public interest” in their policies on contested areas of public policy.
3. **Illustrate consequences:** Use examples to show how narrow or exclusive definitions of public interest can be detrimental towards marginalised and vulnerable communities and to democracy.

II: Empowering bottom-up definitions of public interest

Communities should be encouraged to reclaim and redefine “public interest.” Policymakers can support this by:

4. **Amplifying grassroots efforts:** Share successful cases of initiatives that reflect community-driven definitions of public interest, such as the deliberative democracy practices in Canada, Agenda 21, and the e5-Gemeinde (*energieeffiziente Gemeinden* “energy efficient communities”). Also highlight the existence of initiatives such as the new Competence Centre on Participatory and Deliberative Democracy in the EU.

¹ <https://www.e5-gemeinden.at/english/en/e5-programme>

5. **Establishing solidarity networks:** Create platforms for grassroots initiatives, civil society organisations, and other publics to organise discussions about common interests and how to pursue them within existing mechanisms. This can be done by organising forums, workshops, and platforms for inclusive discussions about public interest.
6. **Providing tools and metrics:** Promote the development of impact criteria and tools to assess the impact and inclusivity of initiatives promoting public interest.
7. **Transforming governance:** Establish multi-sector networks across civil society and academia to explore paths to transform the existing governance mechanisms towards more transparency and accountability.

III: Pluralising singular concepts (publics, interests, democracies)

The meaning of the term "public", "interest" and "democracy" must be reimagined as dynamic, diverse and inclusive. Policymakers and communities can support this by:

8. **Raising awareness:** Launch public campaigns to highlight the need for a shift to inclusive vision-building and evolving definitions of public interest tied to changing and place-based societal contexts. **Raising awareness:** Launch public campaigns to highlight the need for a shift to inclusive vision-building and evolving definitions of public interest tied to changing and place-based societal contexts.
9. **Establishing feedback loops:** Regularly evaluate how public interest is defined and implemented, ensuring its efficiency, inclusivity, and alignment with democratic values.
10. **Promoting pluralism:** Recognise that public interest may differ across urban and rural areas, majority and minority groups, and other social divides. Policies should reflect these diverse perspectives.

Findings from ACCTING

Key insights from the ACCTING research for policymakers and communities:

- "Public interest" often excludes marginalised voices and reflects the perspective of dominant groups. It is also the other way around; when tensions arise between the communities and authorities, what the public interest is in that situation is usually clear and thereby needs to be clarified through regular meetings.

Example: In Portugal, the municipal policies of disaster risk management in the greater Lisbon area require urban transformation projects and resettlement in one of the most disadvantaged neighbourhoods, populated predominantly by the migrants. The frequent floods and heat waves have created serious life hazards, however the communities resist moving due to many factors. They lack adequate knowledge about the resettlement sites, fear dissipation of their communities which provide a social safety net and believe that they can adapt to the disasters in their given location. In this situation while public interest is defined as a general societal resilience against disasters, the vulnerable groups do not see its implementation into their unique conditions.

- Authorities frequently use the term to avoid transparency and suppress dissent.

Example: In a mid-sized city in Sweden, a new transport system that prioritises bus traffic over car traffic on the city's main thoroughfare caused considerable protests. The policymakers behind the project argued that this system was in the public's interest, but that the public does not always understand what is in their best interest. As they reasoned, the public does not have the knowledge required to predict what transport needs the city will have in ten years. The expert knowledge of the traffic planning department trumped other knowledge claims and public consultation was actively avoided as it was seen as mainly a hindrance to achieve a necessary transition. Also clear from this case was that the public was defined as the "broad masses", and the impact on marginalised group was given limited attention.

- Bottom-up and grassroots initiatives can crucially contribute to redefining public interest in more inclusive and democratic ways, as reflected through ACCTING's research (see the better stories below).

Better Stories

In ACCTING we use 'better stories', a concept borrowed from Dina Georgis², to refer to promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices.

Akbelen Forest Solidarity³ collective in Turkey: an environmental struggle to protect forests threatened by coal mining redefined public interest based on the rights of people to a healthy environment and to continue to make a sustainable living, and the right of future generations to inherit an undisturbed and unpolluted environment. This clashed with the state's definition of public interest, which was based on the energy needs of industry and general use and could not prevent the forest from being destroyed. This case provides alternative perspectives on public interest that can also be relevant for other environmental struggles. Even though the forest was eventually destroyed and the mining project expanded, this struggle strengthened the case for environmental rights as a principle for public interest. The Akbelen collective continues its forest watch right by the destroyed forest to continue documenting the environmental harm produced by the mine and provide support to other local anti-mining forest defence movements across the country.

Echoversity⁴ is a pilot project carried out by the Ecomuseum in Greece. In the project, the civil society organisers closely worked with the transhumance communities, scientists, and ordinary citizens to create sound maps of the transhumance routes. The project was born out of the goal to support the transhumance communities, whose ecological and traditional knowledge have historically been unacknowledged through sustainable tourism while also increasing public engagement with and knowledge of natural areas. The public engagement models varied from increased interactions between environmental scientists and citizens to festivals around local cultures. The project showcased a participatory model of forging a common agenda across different public sectors around the ultimate goal of sustainability and environmental protection.

² Georgis, D. (2013). *The better story: Queer affects from the Middle East*. Suny Press.

³ https://ikizkoydireniyor.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/AKBELEN-FOREST_INFO_NOTE_OCTOBER-2023_s.pdf

⁴ <https://ecomuseumzagori.gr/en/echoversity/>

References

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About ACCTING

ACCTING is an EU-funded project aiming to understand the impact of Green Deal policies on vulnerable groups, prevent inequalities, and produce knowledge and innovations to advance behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

Running until May 2025 and based on two research cycles, ACCTING mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal, focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies.

Find out more about the project and discover more factsheets at <https://accting.eu>

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